

IAC-25-B1.6.9

Witnessing with Earth Observation: Using Sentinel-2 Data to Assess Environmental Destruction in Gaza

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Abstract

Assessing environmental destruction in war-affected regions presents significant challenges due to restricted ground access, damaged infrastructure, and ongoing security concerns. Traditional field-based data collection is often infeasible in these areas, making Earth Observation (EO) an essential tool for monitoring environmental changes and degradation. The increasing availability of high-resolution and frequent satellite imagery offers a means to assess war-induced environmental impacts remotely, providing critical information for damage assessment, humanitarian response, and long-term recovery planning. This study employs Sentinel-2 satellite imagery to analyze the environmental consequences of genocide in Gaza, focusing on changes in vegetation, water, and land health. By utilizing several environmental indices, we evaluate the extent of destruction across different ecological and urban zones, with particular emphasis on surface water and moisture. Our results demonstrate that EO can reliably detect damage to key infrastructure, such as wastewater treatment plants, while also producing ambiguous signals in farmland and vehicle corridors that cannot be interpreted without local testimony and ground truth. By applying image-processing techniques, this study provides a framework for rapid and preliminary environmental impact assessment while also acknowledging the ethical responsibility to avoid over-interpretation. Furthermore, we discuss the technical and ethical challenges associated with EO-based monitoring during genocide, including limitations of spectral indices, incomplete mapping data, and the need to protect privacy and dignity when analyzing displacement areas. The findings underscore the necessity of integrating satellite-derived environmental data with local knowledge in order to produce meaningful outputs. EO data can inform restoration strategies by identifying priority areas for soil rehabilitation and water management, but must be treated as complementary to on-the-ground knowledge. By demonstrating both the potential and limitations of EO to fill critical data gaps, this study advocates for its careful application in documenting and understanding the long-term environmental impacts of genocide.

Keywords: Earth Observation, Gaza, Sentinel-2, Surface Water, Environmental Destruction, Genocide

Acronyms

EO	Earth Observation
FA	Forensic Architecture
mNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDMI	Normalized Difference Moisture Index
RSWIR	Red- Shortwave Infrared

sewage overflow, and contamination of the aquifer that is already under extreme stress. These attacks deliberately undermine the ecological basis of life in Gaza, exacerbating famine, disease, and long-term displacement [1,2].

Documentation of these acts is obstructed by deliberate silencing. Journalists have been killed in record numbers and international observers are systematically denied access [3]. In this environment of enforced invisibility, Earth Observation (EO) provides one of the only available tools for independent monitoring. EO satellites orbit the Earth on a continuous basis, generating publicly available imagery even when the ground is rendered inaccessible. These datasets allow researchers to witness large-scale destruction that would otherwise remain hidden.

1. Introduction

In the ongoing genocide in Gaza [1], environmental destruction has become both a consequence and a deliberate strategy of violence [2]. Agricultural lands, greenhouses, orchards, and other life-sustaining systems have been repeatedly destroyed. Water treatment plants, desalination facilities, wells, and sewage infrastructure have been systematically targeted, resulting in flooding,

The Palestine Space Institute (PSI) is a pioneering and visionary think tank that stands at the forefront of space ethics and the responsible use of outer space [4]. This

project falls under PSI's theme "Space for Palestine," feeding into a new Earth Observation research direction.

The purpose of this study is to apply Sentinel-2 satellite data to assess environmental destruction in Gaza. We use vegetation and water indices to identify changes between February 2023, before the genocide, and February 2025, after more than a year of devastation. The analysis focuses on vegetation moisture, water stress, surface water pooling, and soil versus standing water. The results provide insight into how targeted destruction has impacted agricultural zones and water infrastructure.

This study is also an ethical act of witnessing. EO can never replace testimony or local knowledge, but it can supplement them. By presenting both reliable and ambiguous findings, this paper highlights the promise and limitations of EO in the midst of genocide.

2. Background and Motivation

Forensic Architecture's 2024 report provided one of the earliest systematic EO-based studies of environmental destruction in Gaza [5]. Their work used NDVI time series from October 2023 to June 2024 to document widespread agricultural damage. This established a precedent for how EO can be used for genocide forensics and environmental monitoring when ground-based methods are blocked.

However, vegetation indices alone are insufficient to capture the breadth of environmental destruction. Targeting of wastewater treatment facilities, wells, reservoirs, and desalination plants has resulted in widespread changes to surface water and soil saturation. These impacts require different spectral indicators to detect reliably. For this reason, we broadened the analysis to include NDVI, NDMI, mNDWI, and RSWIR. Each index captures different aspects of vegetation and water conditions, allowing us to differentiate between plant health, moisture stress, surface water, and soil water content.

The motivation for this study is twofold. The first is technical. We sought to demonstrate how EO can detect infrastructure-linked changes in vegetation and water even when no field data are available. The second is ethical. EO analysis in genocide carries the risk of misinterpretation and dehumanization. When indices produce signals that can have multiple explanations, researchers must be cautious not to present ambiguous results as definitive findings. Our approach therefore distinguishes clearly between reliable and ambiguous insights.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data and Timeframe

We used Sentinel-2 Level-2A imagery provided by ESA Copernicus. To ensure comparability, we selected February 2023 as a pre-genocide baseline and February 2025 as the post-destruction sample. These months were chosen because weather and crop cycles are relatively consistent, reducing seasonal bias in spectral signals.

3.2 Processing

Images were processed into spectral maps using band math functions. For each index, we produced animated GIFs comparing 2023 and 2025, as well as static difference maps showing percentage change. Geospatial overlays were then applied to link spectral changes to specific facilities.

3.3 Indices

Four spectral indices were selected for this analysis:

- **NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index):** measures vegetation health and overall moisture content.
- **NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index):** measures vegetation water stress, especially in leaves, and complements NDVI.
- **mNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index):** isolates surface water while reducing soil and vegetation noise [6].
- **RSWIR (Red- Short-Wave Infrared):** differentiates soil moisture from standing water, useful in arid contexts [7].

3.4 Infrastructure Data

In addition to the EO data, we cross-referenced our analysis with multiple sources:

- OpenStreetMap (OSM) datasets, the most reliable but incomplete mapping resource for Gaza. This resource is crowdsourced by Palestinians on the ground in Gaza.
- Gaza municipal maps, where available.
- Forensic Architecture data (May-June 2024)
 - Ground invasion routes
 - Status of water tanks and reservoirs
 - Status of water wells
 - Status of wastewater and desalination plants
- OCHA water treatment facility data (2018).

These sources allowed us to contextualize spectral signals, although some areas remained unlabeled and uninterpretable. This is further discussed in the following section.

4. Results

The following sections present the analysis of the selected spectral indices.

4.1 NDVI

Fig. 1. NDVI analysis of Gaza. Left: Sentinel-2 NDVI map from February 2025. Right: Difference map comparing February 2023 and February 2025.

Table 1. NDVI value range

Min	Max	Indicator (EOS)
-1	0	Clouds, water, snow
0	0.1	Bare soil, rocks, sand
0.2	0.3	Moderate vegetation
>0.3	1	Dense vegetation

The NDVI analysis showed major changes between February 2023 and February 2025. The most prominent signal was the flooding detected around the Rafah wastewater treatment plant. The spectral values in this area increased in a way that is consistent with pooled water and saturated soil. This aligns with reports of wastewater plant damage and represents a reliable finding because it is clearly localized to a known facility.

Farmland across Gaza also exhibited increases in NDVI. Speculation might suggest vegetation recovery, but this interpretation cannot be taken at face value. Increased NDVI signals may reflect weeds and opportunistic plants growing in untended areas where farmers no longer have access to their land, or changes in farming practices as communities attempt to survive famine in certain areas, or even a result of the heavy rainfall that occurred in autumn 2024. EO is therefore

reliable in showing that change occurred, but ambiguous in what it represents. Without ground knowledge from farmers or local testimony, no definitive conclusion can be made.

The Netzarim corridor, where ground invasion of the occupation forces is separating North and South Gaza, also appeared bright in the NDVI maps. This may be due to major disturbance from heavy vehicles, which would strip vegetation and disturb soil. However, NDVI is also sensitive to soil reflectance and noise, meaning the brightness could partly be an artefact of the index itself. The corridor is therefore an important finding because it clearly shows disruption, but its precise meaning remains uncertain.

Taken together, NDVI provided reliable confirmation of wastewater flooding and clear evidence of farmland changes, while also raising interpretive challenges in distinguishing causes of those changes.

4.2 NDMI

Fig. 2. NDMI analysis of Gaza. Left: Sentinel-2 NDMI map from February 2025. Right: Difference map comparing February 2023 and February 2025.

Table 2. NDMI value range

Min	Max	Indicator (EOS)
-1	-0.8	Bare soil
-0.8	0	Dryness/drought
0	0.4	Moderate canopy/stress
0.4	0.8	Dense canopy/no stress
0.8	1	Full canopy/waterlogging

NDMI reinforced many of the patterns observed in NDVI. Wastewater plants again stood out clearly, with signals consistent with flooding and saturation. This overlap strengthens the reliability of the wastewater findings, since two indices targeting different aspects of moisture confirmed the same result.

At the same time, NDMI highlighted the same ambiguities found in NDVI. Farmland changes were evident but open to multiple explanations. The Netzarim corridor again appeared bright, reinforcing its importance as a site of disturbance. However, as with NDVI, this brightness could indicate pooled water, compressed soil, or spectral noise. NDMI is also less sensitive in urban areas, which limited its ability to capture changes in densely built-up environments such as Gaza City.

Thus, NDMI supports the reliability of wastewater flooding signals while reinforcing the interpretive uncertainty around farmland and corridor brightness. By confirming some of the same findings as NDVI while also showing its own limitations, NDMI underscores the necessity of cross-index comparison and cautious interpretation.

The mNDWI analysis focused specifically on surface water and produced the clearest results for wastewater infrastructure. Beit Lahia and Sheikh Ajleen wastewater treatment plants showed strong, bright signals consistent with flooding. These findings are significant because mNDWI reduces the influence of soil and vegetation noise, making surface water detection more robust. This strengthens the reliability of the conclusion that wastewater infrastructure was deliberately and systematically compromised.

However, not all mNDWI signals could be linked to mapped facilities. Some bright patches appeared in areas without corresponding infrastructure data in OpenStreetMap or municipal maps. These signals may represent unmapped infrastructure, natural pooling of water, or false positives caused by noise in the dataset. Without ground truth, they remain ambiguous.

mNDWI therefore confirms wastewater flooding as a reliable finding while illustrating the persistent problem of incomplete mapping in Gaza. It highlights how EO can expose changes that cannot be interpreted fully without local verification.

4.3 mNDWI

Fig. 3. mNDWI analysis of Gaza. Left: Sentinel-2 mNDWI map from February 2025. Right: Difference map comparing February 2023 and February 2025.

Table 3. mNDWI value range

Min	Max	Indicator (EOS)
-1	0	Built-up land, vegetation
0.0	1	Water

4.4 RSWIR

Fig. 4. RSWIR analysis of Gaza. Left: Sentinel-2 RSWIR map from February 2025. Right: Difference map comparing February 2023 and February 2025.

Table 4. RSWIR value range

Min	Max	Indicator (Al Ali, 2024)
-0.05	0.12	Soil moisture
0.12		Water

RSWIR provided further confirmation of wastewater plant flooding, repeating the patterns seen in NDVI, NDMI, and mNDWI. The fact that flooding appears consistently across all four indices strengthens confidence in this finding.

At the same time, RSWIR produced one of the clearest examples of EO's limitations. An area flagged as standing water corresponded to the location of heavy bombardment and the presence of large bomb craters. At first, the signal seemed consistent with the hypothesis that craters had filled with rainwater, a plausible interpretation of the spectral data. However, further geospatial investigation with high-resolution imagery revealed that the area was in fact a displacement camp. The spectral signal was a false flag, not water but the reflectance from cleared land and tents. These high resolution images are purposely excluded from this report as they infringe on the privacy and dignity of the individuals in these displacement camps.

This case demonstrates the dangers of interpreting EO signals without verification. It shows how EO can provide signals that appear plausible yet lead to entirely false conclusions if not checked against higher-resolution imagery and local knowledge. It also highlights our ethical duties as researchers with access to such data.

4.5 Summary of Results

The results show a pattern of both reliable and ambiguous findings. Reliable results include flooding at multiple wastewater treatment plants, confirmed consistently across all indices. These findings align with independent knowledge of infrastructure damage and represent strong evidence of environmental destruction.

Ambiguous results include increased farmland vegetation, brightness along the Netzarim corridor, and unmapped bright patches. These signals demonstrate that change occurred but cannot be interpreted definitively without ground truth. The misclassification of a displacement camp as water shows the danger of false interpretation due to the simple nature of these indices, as EO can produce signals that appear plausible but are misleading.

Taken together, the results show that EO provides valuable and credible evidence of environmental destruction during genocide but must be interpreted cautiously and in combination with local knowledge.

5. Discussion

This analysis demonstrates both the strengths and the limits of EO in documenting environmental destruction during genocide in Gaza. The repeated and consistent detection of wastewater plant flooding across all four indices provides strong evidence that EO can reliably capture infrastructure-linked environmental impacts. These findings are significant because they align with independent reports of deliberate targeting of Gaza's water infrastructure. They demonstrate how EO can provide reliable environmental monitoring even when field investigations are blocked.

At the same time, many findings remain ambiguous. Farmland moisture increases, the brightness of the Netzarim corridor, and bright patches not linked to mapped facilities cannot be given definitive interpretations. These results show that EO detects change but does not reveal cause. Without testimonies and local ground surveys, EO cannot distinguish whether vegetation signals represent resilience, abandonment, or rainfall effects. Similarly, the Netzarim corridor appears clearly disturbed but cannot be conclusively attributed to specific processes without local confirmation.

The misclassification of a displacement camp as standing water is the clearest demonstration of EO's limitations. The signal at first seemed entirely plausible, consistent with bomb craters filling with water. Yet closer geospatial investigation revealed it to be an artefact of cleared land and tents. This case illustrates the dangers of relying solely on EO. Without corroborating data, EO can produce convincing but false conclusions.

Ethical considerations are also important in this discussion [8]. EO makes visible not only environmental change but also human suffering. In genocide, displacement camps appear as bright signals on maps, but these signals correspond to spaces where Palestinians are forced to live in tents. Researchers must recognize their duty of care, avoiding voyeurism and dehumanization, protecting dignity, and ensuring that analysis does not reduce human lives to abstract signals.

Overall, EO should be treated as both indispensable and insufficient. It is indispensable because it makes visible the destruction that perpetrators seek to conceal. It is insufficient because it cannot replace testimony and local knowledge. EO is most valuable when integrated into broader frameworks of humanitarian documentation and ecological monitoring, where it complements rather than substitutes human voices.

6. Conclusions

This study used Sentinel-2 indices to analyze environmental destruction in Gaza during the ongoing genocide. The results provide clear evidence of wastewater treatment plant flooding, confirmed across NDVI, NDMI, mNDWI, and RSWIR. These are reliable findings that illustrate EO's capacity to detect targeted damage to critical infrastructure.

Ambiguous findings also emerged in relation to farmland, heavy vehicle corridors, and bright patches unlinked to infrastructure. These results show that EO can reveal where change has occurred but not why it has occurred. The case of the displacement camp misclassified as water demonstrates how EO can produce signals that are plausible yet misleading if not corroborated.

The conclusion is that EO provides essential monitoring capacity during genocide but must always be interpreted with caution. It is a powerful tool of witnessing when human observers are silenced, but it cannot stand alone. Its findings must be integrated with testimonies, municipal data, and local knowledge. Future work should expand time-series analyses to trace patterns of environmental destruction, investigate cumulative impacts of bombardment and heavy vehicle use on soil and water, and pursue partnerships that embed EO within humanitarian and ecological research.

Ultimately, EO can serve as an important tool for justice. It can document the destruction of land and resources, support humanitarian response, and contribute to legal and policy processes addressing genocide. Only when combined with human testimony and local knowledge can EO strengthen the pursuit of justice.

Acknowledgements

PSI is an independent research group with no ties to or funding from any political parties.

We dedicate this work to the resilient people of Gaza, who endure unimaginable hardships and continue to stand strong in the face of oppression.

We extend our gratitude and support to all individuals and communities around the world who are tirelessly fighting for social justice, equality, and the right to live with dignity.

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